

**ASSESSMENT OF TRAIT ANGER AND LEVEL OF
ANGER EXPRESSION STYLES OF STUDENTS WHO STUDIED AT
SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN
TERMS OF SOME VARIABLES**

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Abstract:

This study focused on reviewing trait anger and level of anger expression styles of students who studied at School of Physical Education and Sports of Adnan Menderes University during 2016-2017 academic year in terms of some variables. As data collection tools; "Personal Information Form" and "Trait Anger and Anger Expression Scale" –designed by Spielberger et al. (1988) and adapted by Özer (1994) into Turkish–were employed. Participants' trait anger and anger expression styles were compared in relation to sex, education type (daytime education vs. evening education), playing sports, sportive branches and academic departments. The population of the study was composed of a total of 981 participants who studied at the school of physical education and sports of Adnan Menderes University during 2016-2017 academic year; 633 of whom were male students while 348 of them were female students. Sample of the study was composed of a total of 541 SPES students; 351 of whom were male students while 190 of them were female students. The analyses of the data were analyzed with SPSS 22.0 statistical software. As a result of the normality test (Kolmogorov-Smirnov - Shapiro-Wilk) done at $p < 0.05$ in order to explore whether or not data followed a normal

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distribution; it was determined that data did not follow a normal distribution. For the analyses of the data that did not follow a normal distribution; Mann Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis Tests were performed at $p < 0.05$ for the differences among the groups and thus findings of the study were found. As a result; it was identified that no generalizations about anger and anger expression styles could be made for the participant students of the School of Physical Education and Sports of Adnan Menderes University in terms of sex variable but anger levels of male students were higher, participation in physical education, physical activities and recreational activities reduced anger level, students of recreation department demonstrated higher level of anger as compared to students of other academic departments, sedentary life styles elevated anger level and anger level did not differ in terms of playing team sports or individual sports.

Keywords: anger, anger expression style, university, sports

1. Introduction

Considering the university education process, it covers an important period during which individuals complete both professional and personal development. That young people develop healthy and desired behaviors during this period, placed between adolescence and adulthood, interests both them and other members of the society with whom they will be in contact during their lives. In this sense, when violence, aggression and stress levels go up, anger and anger expression –one of the behavior modes that may harm individuals themselves and other members- becomes more important. It is reported that anger positively affects psychosocial growth, interpersonal relations and individual happiness when it is handled well; on the other hand, it produces destructive outcomes for individuals themselves, their family, workplace and society when it is mishandled (Tatlıođlu and Karaca, 2013).

For Budak (2000); anger is described as “an intense negative emotion which is felt in cases of such situations as frustration, violation, threat, deprivation, restriction, etc. and may generally results in aggressive behaviors towards the object or person that causes anger. What is important in this description of anger is how one will show and express his/her behaviors in such situation as frustration, violation, threat, deprivation, restriction, etc. No matter what causes anger, how one will respond this negative situation matters more because reactions one demonstrates in case of any negative situation are different. Actually, it is reported that when individuals get angry, they may demonstrate numerous different behaviors such as expressing anger directly,

using mutual communication, thinking before giving a reaction, showing physical and verbal aggression against individuals and objects, keeping anger inside, controlling anger, self-criticism, changing the subject in question, and demonstrating passive-aggressive behaviors (cited by Özkamalı and Buğa, 2010). It is argued that what is more important in this situation is severity of anger felt by individuals and how much control they have upon these feelings. Anger basically relates to three objects: anger towards individuals themselves, anger towards others and anger towards events individuals are exposed to (Soykan, 2003). In literature, different behaviors in individuals' anger and anger expression styles are classified as anger-control, anger-in and anger-out.

According to this classification;

Anger-out is defined as expressing and releasing anger feeling verbally or behaviorally and an adaptive reaction to stress caused by anger.

Anger-in is defined as an alternative adaptive mechanism used for anger factors by redirection of the anger to the self.

Anger-control is associated with the degree to which one keeps anger under control or how much one tends to keep calm; experiences to control anger expressions through personal reactions (Starner and Peters, 2004). Depending on individual differences, anger and anger expression styles change. It is reported that anger expression and anger control differ according to culture, individual expectations, learned behaviors, family behavioral modes, educational status, age and sex (Freidman, 1993). Besides; although anger is a feeling experienced at all ages, it is not possible to argue that anger has same qualities at all ages and is caused by the same causes. Therefore, it is stated that anger should specifically be examined in relation to each age period (Özmen et al., 2016).

Studies on anger and anger expression styles done in Turkey mostly include disadvantageous students, primary school students, secondary school students and university students but studies that recruit students who study at schools of physical education and sports and sports sciences faculties are very limited (Akpınar et al. 2012; Nas et al. 2016).

Considering the fact that teacher candidates who study at schools of physical education and sports and sports sciences faculties may be employed as teachers, coaches, sports managers, recreationist, and SPES teachers for the disabled individuals; they will be doing a profession that improves and contributes to children, adolescents and adults not only physically but also personally, socially, psychologically and mentally. Therefore, it is very crucial to investigate anger and anger expression styles of SPES students in terms of exploring the existing situation.

2. Method

2.1 Study Model

The study was designed in screening model and descriptive statistics model. Screening Model is a research approach that aims to describe a situation either as it was before or as it is now. The event, individual or object that is the subject of the study is described as it is in its own conditions. No efforts are made to change or to affect them (Karasar, 2014).

2.2 Population and Sample

The population of the study was composed of a total of 981 participants who studied at Teaching, Coaching, Sports Management and Recreation Departments of School of Physical Education and Sports of Adnan Menderes University during 2016-2017 academic year; 633 of whom were male students while 348 of them were female students. Sample of the study was composed of a total of 541 SPES students; 351 of whom were male students while 190 of them were female students.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

As data collection tools; "Personal Information Form" and "Trait Anger and Anger Expression Scale" –designed by Spielberger et al. (1988) and adapted by Özer (1994) into Turkish- were employed. Participants' trait anger and anger expression styles were compared in relation to sex, education type (daytime education vs. evening education), playing sports, sportive branches and academic departments. Trait Anger and Anger Expression Scale –which was designed by Spielberger et al. (1988) was used. Spielberger categorizes anger feeling into "state anger" and "trait anger". "State anger" refers to subjective state of mood in which such subjective emotions as tension, nervousness and fury are experienced in case of frustrated behaviors or injustice perceptions while "trait anger" is described as a dispositional characteristic that reflects how often anger is experienced. Anger-control, anger-in and anger-out are the dimensions that reflect how anger is expressed (Özer 1994). The scale is consisted of 34 items. The first 10 items reflect how often one experiences state anger while the other 24 items reflect how one expresses anger –namely; anger expression styles-. There are three subscales in Anger Expression Styles Scale: anger-in (8 items), anger-out (8 items) and anger-control (8 items). Turkish validity and reliability tests were performed by Özer (1994). Cronbach alpha coefficients of Trait Anger Scale were found to be ranging between .67 and .92. Cronbach alpha coefficients of subscales of Anger Expression Scale were between .80 and .90 for anger-control, .69 and .91 for anger-out and .58 and .76 for anger-in.

2.4 Data Analysis

The analyses of the data obtained from the participants were analyzed with SPSS 22.0 statistical software. The normality test (Kolmogorov-Smirnov - Shapiro-Wilk) was done at $p < 0.05$ in order to explore whether or not data followed a normal distribution and it was found that data did not follow a normal distribution. For the analyses of the data that did not follow a normal distribution; Mann Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis Tests were performed at $p < 0.05$ for the differences among the groups and thus findings of the study were found.

3. Findings

Table 1: Normality Test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Trait anger	.076	541	.000	.982	541	.000
Anger-in	.075	541	.000	.978	541	.000
Anger-out	.089	541	.000	.977	541	.000
Anger control	.069	541	.000	.988	541	.000

When Table 1 was examined; variables of trait anger, anger-in, anger-out and anger control did not follow a normal distribution.

Table 2: Comparisons of Anger Scale and its subscales in terms of sex variable

Trait anger	N	Rank	Sd	U	p
Female	190	253.80	2	36.613.000	0.59
Male	351	280.31			
Anger-in					
Female	190	250.07	2	37.321.000	0.22
Male	351	282.33			
Anger-out					
Female	190	243.56	2	38.559.000	.003
Male	351	285.85			
Anger control					
Female	190	268.27	2	33.863.000	.765
Male	351	272.48			
Total anger					
Female	190	244.11	2	38.455.000	.003
Male	351	285.56			

According to Mann Whitney U Test results concerning participants' Anger Scale and its subscales in terms of sex variable; it was identified that there was significant difference between female participants and male participants in relation to total scores of anger scale and scores of anger-in and anger-out subscales ($p < 0.05$). Accordingly; male participants reported higher scores of anger scale and anger-in and anger-out subscales as compared to female participants. As for scores of trait anger and anger-control subscales; there were not any significant differences in terms of sex variable ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3: Comparisons of Anger Scale and its subscales in terms of education type variable

Trait anger	N	Rank	Sd	U	p
Daytime Education	345	263.16	2	36.516.000	.121
Evening Education	196	284.81			
Anger-in					
Daytime Education	345	267.43	2	35.043.000	.479
Evening Education	196	277.29			
Anger-out					
Daytime Education	345	264.28	2	36.128.500	.184
Evening Education	196	282.83			
Anger control					
Daytime Education	345	272.01	2	33.460.000	.841
Evening Education	196	269.21			
Total anger					
Daytime Education	345	265.93	2	35.559.500	.317
Evening Education	196	279.93			

According to Mann Whitney U Test results concerning participants' Anger Scale and its subscales in terms of education type variable; it was found that there were not any significant differences between total scores of anger scale and scores of the subscales ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4: Comparisons of Anger Scale and its subscales in terms of playing sports variable

Trait anger	N	Rank	Sd	U	p
Athlete	331	274.27	2	33.673.000	.541
Sedentary	210	265.85			
Anger-in					
Athlete	331	271.81	2	34.488.000	.880
Sedentary	210	269.73			

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Anger-out					
Athlete	331	282.29	2	31.017.000	.034
Sedentary	210	253.20			
Anger control					
Athlete	331	277.10	2	32.737.500	.254
Sedentary	210	261.39			
Total anger					
Athlete	331	279.13	2	32.064.000	.129
Sedentary	210	258.19			

According to Mann Whitney U Test results concerning participants' Anger Scale and its subscales in terms of playing sports variable; no significant differences were found among scores of anger scale, trait anger, anger-control and anger-in ($p>0.05$). Yet, a statistically significant difference was found between sportive participants and sedentary participants in terms of anger-out subscale ($p<0.05$). It was seen that the difference was on behalf of those who played sports.

Table 5: Kruskal Wallis Test results of the participants in terms of academic department variable

Trait anger	N	Rank	Sd	Kruskal Wallis Test	p
Teaching	89	245.93	3	13.786	.003
Coaching	187	269.37			
Management	119	246.20			
Recreation	146	308.59			
Anger-in					
Teaching	89	249.24	3	10.906	.012
Coaching	187	276.17			
Management	119	243.18			
Recreation	146	300.32			
Anger-out					
Teaching	89	267.24	3	6.187	.103
Coaching	187	272.39			
Management	119	245.04			
Recreation	146	292.68			
Anger control					
Teaching	89	252.76	3	5.727	.126
Coaching	187	287.20			
Management	119	281.39			
Recreation	146	252.90			
Total anger					

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Teaching	89	246.60	3	8.773	.032
Coaching	187	279.76			
Management	119	247.03			
Recreation	146	294.19			

According to Kruskal Wallis Test results of the participants that reflected Anger Scale and its subscales in terms of academic department variable; it was found that there were significant differences among total scores of anger, trait anger score, and anger-in score ($p < 0.05$) while no significant differences were found among anger-out and anger-control subscales ($p > 0.05$). The significant difference between anger scale and its subscales were found to be against favor of students who studied at recreation department.

Table 6: Kruskal Wallis Test results of the participants in terms of sportive branch variable

Trait anger	N	Rank	Sd	Kruskal Wallis Test	p
Sedentary	161	259.99	3	1.308	.520
Team sports	244	273.22			
Individual sports	136	280.06			
Anger-in					
Sedentary	161	259.96	3	1.309	.520
Team sports	244	278.05			
Individual sports	136	271.41			
Anger-out					
Sedentary	161	248.22	3	6.105	.047
Team sports	244	287.23			
Individual sports	136	268.85			
Anger-control					
Sedentary	161	260.70	3	1.386	.500
Team sports	244	271.66			
Individual sports	136	282.02			
Total Anger					
Sedentary	161	252.10	3	3.546	.170
Team sports	244	281.63			
Individual sports	136	274.31			

According to the results of the participants concerning Kruskal Wallis Test performed in terms of academic department variable; it was found that there was a significant difference in anger-out scores ($p < 0.05$). Accordingly, anger-out scores of participants that played team sports were found to be higher than those participants who played

individual sports and those sedentary participants. Despite this, no significant differences among anger scale and other subscales were found ($p>0.05$).

4. Results and Discussion

In terms of sex variable of the participants, it was identified that there was considerably significant difference between female participants and male participants in relation to total scores of anger scale and scores of anger-in and anger-out subscales ($p<0.05$). Accordingly, male participants reported higher total scores of anger scale and scores of anger-in and anger-out subscales as compared to female participants. Some studies in the literature supported our findings (Erkek et al., 2006; Köksal and Gençdoğan, 2007; Yöndem and Bıçakçı, 2008; Kırımoğlu, 2010) and this above mentioned finding was explained by Şahin (2005) that patriarchal order, dating back to primeval era and surviving until today, has been consolidated anger among men as an vital instrument of attack and defense and male anger has been taken normally by the society. On the other hand, as for trait anger and anger-control subscales there were not any significant differences in terms of sex variable ($p>0.05$). It is also reported that findings of some studies concerning sex variable contradicted our findings (Stoner and Spencer, 1987; Bostancı et al. 2006;) while some others did not find any difference in anger scale and its subscales in terms of sex variable (Kopper, 1993; Baygöl, 1997; Bilge, 1997; Olmuş, 2001; Balkaya and Şahin, 2003; Babaoğlu, 2007; Gök, 2009; Certel and Bahadır, 2012; Üzüm, et al.2016; Demir et al. 2017).

It is obvious that in literature there are different findings and outcomes in relation to trait anger and anger expression styles in terms of sex variable and therefore no generalizations can be made. However; due to the fact that male participants had higher level of total anger score and anger-in and anger-out scores and all these studies demonstrated that participants' trait anger and anger expression styles were influenced by such factors as different cultural, geographical, morals and manners; we may argue that different results were obtained.

According to another finding obtained in the current study and education type variable; it was found that there were not any significant differences between total scores of anger scale and scores of the subscales ($p>0.05$). Accordingly, it may be suggested that anger and anger expression styles of the students of daytime education and evening education did not change. However, in literature there were no studies on education type and anger and anger expression styles. Therefore, we may recommend that prospective studies should examine this variable, too.

According to results of analyses in terms of participants' playing sports; it was found that there were not any significant differences among total score of anger scale, trait anger score, anger-control score and anger-in score ($p>0.05$). But a statistically significant difference was found between sportive participants and sedentary participants in terms of anger-out subscale ($p<0.05$). It was noted that the difference was on behalf of those sportive participants who played sports. Literature confirms that participation in physical education and sports, physical activities, recreational activities and playing sports actively support one's physical, mental, psychological and social development; which –it is obvious- has created a general attitude. In literature, a study on anger level of sportive and sedentary individuals pointed out that those playing sports showed lower scores of anger scale and its subscales (Üzüm, 2016). Similarly, another study, concurring with the findings of the study of Üzüm and the current study, indicated that there was a significant correlation between self-esteem and trait anger and anger expression style scales (Certel and Bahadır, (2012). According to Certel and Bahadır (2012), scores of anger scale and its subscale scores of sportive participants with high self-esteem were lower than sedentary participants. In sum; we may conclude that participation in physical education and sports, physical activities, recreational activities and playing sports actively enhance self-esteem but reduce anger level.

According to the results of the analyses concerning academic department variable; it was found that there was a significant difference in anger-out ($p<0.05$). Accordingly, anger-out scores of participants that played team sports were found to be higher than those participants who played individual sports and those sedentary participants. Despite this, no significant differences among anger scale and other subscales were found ($p>0.05$). In the study of Certel and Bahadır, (2012) titled as "Analysis of the Relationship between Self Esteem, Trait Anger and Anger Expression in Athletes Making Team Sports" athletes playing in basketball, handball and football teams did not demonstrate considerable differences in trait anger, anger-in, anger-out and anger control; which supported our finding on the whole. However; the study of Demir et al. (2017) titled as "Anger Expression Styles of Athletes" reported that subscale scores of controlled anger expression styles of athletes playing team sports were higher than those playing individual sports and that subscale scores of anger-out anger expression styles of those playing individual sports were higher than those playing team sports. But no significant differences were found in other subscales of anger expression styles scale (Demir et al. 2017). Contrary to the findings of the current study; findings of Demir et al. (2017) demonstrated that scores of anger-out anger among those playing individual sports were higher than those playing team sports. The different results obtained from these studies may have been caused by personality structure of

the participants of team sports and those of individual sports and by the various factors that increased anger feeling in sports setting and competition setting (for example; being subjected to aggression and attitudes of coaches, spectators, opponent and family, etc.). Actually, in the study of Karagün and Çağlayan (2014) it was identified that scores of the athletes that were subjected to aggression were higher than those that were not subjected to aggression; which is in line with our conclusion above. In order to generalize; there is a need for studies that will be composed of larger samples and will be focusing on factors increasing anger levels.

In results of the analyses done in relation to participants' academic department variable and anger scale and its subscales; it was found that there were significant differences among total scores of anger scale, trait anger scores, and anger-in scores ($p < 0.05$) while no significant differences were found among anger-out and anger-control subscale ($p > 0.05$). The significant difference between anger scale and its subscales were found to be against favor of students who studied at recreation department; which may have been resulted from the fact that recreation department could not gain public popularity in the eye of people and lacked public employment opportunities because finance ministry did not recognize recreation department as a profession. When studies in literature were investigated, no studies -in favor of or against the sample group of the current study- were found. However; some studies done with candidate teachers of different academic branches and teachers of different academic branches (pre-school teachers, primary school teachers, psychological counseling and guidance teachers, English teachers, music and painting teachers) did not reveal any significant differences, either (Babaoğlan, 2007; Yöndem and Bıçakçı, 2008).

As a result, following conclusions may be drawn for the participants of the current study:

- No generalization could be made about anger and anger expression styles in terms of sex variable but anger level of male participants was higher,
- Participation in physical education and sports, physical activities and recreational activities reduced anger level,
- Students of recreation department had higher anger level than the students of other academic departments,
- Sedentary life styles elevated anger level,
- Anger and anger expression styles did not differ in terms of team sports or individual sports but those who were engaged with team sports had higher anger-out scores than those who were engaged with individual sports and those who were sedentary.

Results obtained from the current study cannot be generalized because it included only students who studied at the School of Physical Education and Sports of Adnan Menderes University. Therefore, in order to draw generalizations, there is a need for studies that will recruit different students from different schools.

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